

EXERGETIC EVALUATION OF THE HEAT SUPPLY SYSTEM WITH SOLAR REFLECTORS IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE SOUTH OF UZBEKISTAN

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The exergy assessment of the agricultural building during the period of the lowest outdoor temperature (January) of solar radiation is taken into account by reflectors. The results obtained confirm the effectiveness of the building + reflector system.

Key words: exergy assessment; heat supply; thermal efficiency; north side; solar reflectors.

The degree of thermodynamic perfection of the system of flat reflectors installed on the north side of the building [1] can be assessed by the exergy indicators of its efficiency - the exergy efficiency factor. When determining the exergy efficiency of a system of flat reflectors installed on the north side of a building with solar heating, we accept the following conditions:

- in the first approximation, the useful exergy E_{us} is the exergy of solar radiation that passed through the light opening E_{op} ;
- as the exergy of the incident solar radiation, the exergy of the solar radiation incident on the surface of the reflector is taken;
- the flow of scattered (diffuse) solar radiation is not taken into account.

Taking into account the accepted conditions, the exergy efficiency of η_e reflectors is determined by the ratio of the fluxes of useful exergy of solar radiation $E_{us} = E_{pa}$, passed through the aperture, and the exergy of solar radiation end incident on the plane of the reflector:

$$\eta_e = E_{us} / E_{fal} = E_{pa} / E_{fal}. \quad (1)$$

The exergy E_{pa} of the solar radiation that has passed through the aperture is determined by the formula [2]:

$$E_{pa} = S_{pa} \eta_t. \quad (2)$$

The flux of solar radiation S_{pa} passed through the aperture [1]:

$$S_{pa} = S_{\perp} F_{lig} K R ; \quad (3)$$

where $S_{\perp}$ - is the flux of direct solar radiation to the surface perpendicular to the rays;

F_{lig} is the surface area of the light aperture;

K - coefficient of light transmission of direct solar radiation by a light aperture;

R - is the specular reflection coefficient of the reflector surface.

Thermal efficiency η_t of the reversible Carnot cycle in the temperature range T_t and T_0

$$\eta_t = \frac{T_t - T_o}{T_t}; \quad (4)$$

where T_t - is the air temperature in the room;

T_o - outside air temperature.

Exergy of solar radiation E_{fal} incident on the plane of reflectors:

$$E_{fal} = S_{fal} \psi . \quad (5)$$

The flux of direct solar radiation incident S_{fal} on the surface of the reflector:

$$S_{fal} = S_{\perp} F_p \cos i ; \quad (6)$$

where F_r - is the surface area of the reflector;

i - angle of incidence of direct solar radiation on the plane of the reflector.

Coefficient of solar radiation exergy dependence on ambient temperature [2]:

$$\psi = 1 - \frac{1}{3} \frac{T_o}{T} \left[4 - \left(\frac{T_o}{T} \right)^3 \right]; \quad (7)$$

where $T = 5762$ K is the effective surface temperature of the solar photosphere.

Consider the exergy efficiency of reflectors for December 21, 2019 - the day of the winter solstice in the conditions of Karshi. Table 1 shows the temperature regime of outdoor air and indoors during insolation.

Table 1

τ , hour	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
T_o , K	275,3	276,3	277,7	279,3	281,4	283,3	284,4	284,6	284,3
T_t , K	291	292,5	294,3	296,2	297,4	298	297,7	296,6	294,8

With the given values of T_t and T_o , the thermal efficiency changes in the range $\eta_t=0.0356...0.0564$; solar radiation exergy dependence coefficient on ambient temperature $\psi=0.934...0.936$.

On fig. Figures 1 and 2 show graphs of daily changes in incident and transmitted direct solar radiation.

On fig. Figures 3 and 4 show graphs of the daily change in the exergy of the simplest solar radiation and that incident on the reflector plane.

On fig. Figure 5 shows a graph of the daily change in the exergy efficiency of flat solar reflectors installed on the north side of the building. Exergy efficiency varies within $\eta_e=2.79...5.38\%$.

Fig.1. Change in direct solar radiation S_{fal} incident on the surface of reflectors, W/m²: 1 - 1, 2 - 1_l, 3 - 1_r reflectors

Fig.2. Change in direct solar radiation S_{pas} passing through the light aperture, W/m²: 1 - 1, 2 - 1_l, 3 - 1_r reflectors

Fig. 3. Change in exergy E_{pas} , transmitted solar radiation, W/m²:

W/m^2 : 1 - 1, 2 - 1_l, 3 - 1_r reflectors

Fig. 4. Changes in the exergy E_{fal} of solar radiation incident on the surface of reflectors: W/m^2 : 1 - 1, 2 - 1_l, 3 - 1_r reflectors

Rice. 5. Exergy efficiency of solar reflectors $\eta_e, \%$

With the given values of T_t and T_0 , the thermal efficiency changes in the range $\eta_t=0.0356...0.0564$; solar radiation exergy dependence coefficient on ambient temperature $\psi=0.934...0.936$.

Given:

- graphs of daily changes in incident and transmitted direct solar radiation;
- graphs of diurnal change in the exergy of the simplest solar radiation and incident on the plane of the reflector;
- graph of the daily change in the exergy efficiency of flat solar reflectors installed on the north side of the building. Exergy efficiency varies within $\eta_e=2,9...5,5 \%$.

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